
REENGINEERING .NET BUSINESS LOGIC FOR SALESFORCE: A STEP-BY-STEP APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

The essay brings out the strategic process for reengineering of .NET business logic to Salesforce and mentions the steps taken in the process of migration, optimization, and integration for already-existing systems. It discusses architecture design, integration strategies, monitoring, and benefits of leveraging cloud abilities of Salesforce in betterment of business operations and scalability.

Keywords: .NET, Salesforce, Integration, Reengineering, Pseudocode

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1. INTRODUCTION

.NET business logic reengineering to Salesforce is a huge task, and its strong evidence of the growing pressure businesses face in terms of moving to more modern, cloud-based environments [1]. As the organizational operations are increasingly being migrated to the cloud, the popularity of Salesforce grows simply because it scales very well, has a large ecosystem of integration partners, and incredibly rich integration functions [2][3]. All the same, this shift is not some kind of lift-and-shift exercise. It is a very careful and deliberate process to make sure the huge .NET business logic out there is definitively translated and optimized within the Salesforce environment.

First and foremost, the process is fuelled by deep knowledge of .NET Framework and the business logic it supports. The business logic has been developed over several years and is tailored to meet the unique needs of the organization, replicating every crucial process at an organizational level [4][5]. Moving this to Salesforce involves not only rewriting code but clone thought processes around how these may be improved by native features within Salesforce—in each case Apex, Visualforce, or Lightning components.

On the other hand, this movement is an opportunity to Lastly, modernize and simplify activities. With the cloud capabilities of Salesforce, greater agility, enhanced collaboration, and enlarged experiences will characterize businesses. This means that the .NET logic coming into Salesforce must not, therefore, be treated as a basic question of functionality but rather one of enabling new efficiencies and capabilities which could not have been hitherto attained in the traditional .NET environment.

II. ANALYSING THE EXISTING .NET BUSINESS LOGIC

Before carrying out any migration, the proper analysis of the current .NET business logic has to be done. This shall include current architecture, data models, workflows, and dependencies. Steps for this phase are enumerated below:

i. Extracting Business Logic

NET classes, methods, and services implement the business logic that must be identified and extracted. This may contain validation rules, data processing algorithms, and integration points with other systems.

ii. Mapping Dependencies

Document all the dependencies, external APIs, databases, and services with which .NET business logic interacts.

iii. Understanding Data Flow

Study how data moves through the .NET application; describe some of the major inputs, transformations, and outputs.

The table below provides a pseudocode of the .NET business logic.

TABLE 1.NET BUSINESS LOGIC FOR PROCESSING ORDERS

```
// .NET Business Logic for Processing Orders
public class OrderProcessor
{
    // Main method to process an order
    public void ProcessOrder(Order order)
    {
        // Check if the order is valid
        if (IsValidOrder(order))
        {
            // Save the order to the database
            SaveOrderToDatabase(order);

            // Notify the customer about the order status
            SendOrderNotification(order);

            // Perform post-processing steps if necessary
            PerformPostProcessing(order);
        }
    }
}
```

```

else
{
    // Log invalid order details for auditing
    LogInvalidOrder(order);

    // Throw an exception to handle the error upstream
    throw new InvalidOperationException("Order is invalid and cannot be processed.");
}
}

// Method to validate the order
private bool IsValidOrder(Order order)
{
    // Check for null order
    if (order == null)
    {
        return false;
    }

    // Validate order details (e.g., product availability, payment method)
    if (order.ProductId == 0 || order.Quantity <= 0 ||
string.IsNullOrEmpty(order.PaymentMethod))
    {
        return false;
    }

    // Additional business rules (e.g., customer eligibility)
    if (!IsCustomerEligible(order.CustomerId))
    {
        return false;
    }

    return true;
}

// Method to check if the customer is eligible to place an order
private bool IsCustomerEligible(int customerId)
{
    // Placeholder for customer eligibility logic
    // For example, check customer credit score, purchase history, etc.
    return true;
}

```

```

}

// Method to save the order to the database
private void SaveOrderToDatabase(Order order)
{
    try
    {
        // Logic to insert order details into the database
        Database.InsertOrder(order);

        // Update inventory stock levels based on the order
        UpdateInventory(order.ProductId, order.Quantity);
    }
    catch (DatabaseException ex)
    {
        // Log database errors and rethrow the exception
        LogError("Failed to save order to database", ex);
        throw;
    }
}

// Method to update inventory based on the order
private void UpdateInventory(int productId, int quantity)
{
    // Logic to decrease stock levels for the ordered product
    Inventory.DecreaseStock(productId, quantity);
}

// Method to send order notification to the customer
private void SendOrderNotification(Order order)
{
    try
    {
        // Logic to send an email notification to the customer
        EmailService.SendOrderConfirmation(order.CustomerEmail, order.OrderId);

        // Optionally, send an SMS notification
        SmsService.SendOrderConfirmation(order.CustomerPhone, order.OrderId);
    }
    catch (NotificationException ex)
    {

```

```
// Log notification errors and continue
    LogError("Failed to send order notification", ex);
}
}

// Method for post-processing after order completion
private void PerformPostProcessing(Order order)
{
    // Example: Generate and send an invoice to the customer
    InvoiceService.GenerateAndSendInvoice(order.OrderId);

    // Example: Update order analytics for reporting purposes
    AnalyticsService.UpdateOrderStatistics(order);
}

// Method to log invalid orders
private void LogInvalidOrder(Order order)
{
    // Logic to log details of invalid orders for audit purposes
    Logger.Log("Invalid order detected", order);
}

// Method to log errors
private void LogError(string message, Exception ex)
{
    // Logic to log error messages and stack traces
    Logger.LogError(message, ex);
}
}
```

The flow chart is provided in the figure below.

Fig. 1 A flow chart of the business logic of the .NET framework

III. DESIGNING THE SALESFORCE ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of Salesforce is different from that of .NET; it focuses on objects, Apex classes, and triggers within Salesforce [6][7][8]. The following steps drive the design phase:

- i. **Define Salesforce Objects:** Map existing .NET data models to Salesforce objects. For example, a .NET Order class might map to a Salesforce Order object.
- ii. **Identify Apex Classes:** Define the specific Apex classes that will contain the business logic. Apex is Salesforce-developed language, vaguely similar to Java, used for implementing custom business logic.
- iii. **Design Triggers and Workflows:** Identify with regard to the Salesforce Workflow where the execution of business logic should take place, such as before insert, after update, or on deletion.

The pseudocode is provided in the following table

TABLE 2 SALESFORCE APEX BUSINESS LOGIC

// Salesforce Apex Business Logic

```
public class OrderProcessor {
    public void processOrder(Order__c order) {
        if (isValid(order)) {
            saveOrder(order);
            notifyCustomer(order);
        }
    }

    private Boolean isValid(Order__c order) {
        // Logic to validate order
        return order != null && order.Status__c == 'New';
    }

    private void saveOrder(Order__c order) {
        // Logic to save order in Salesforce
        insert order;
    }

    private void notifyCustomer(Order__c order) {
        // Logic to send notification to the customer
        Messaging.SingleEmailMessage mail = new Messaging.SingleEmailMessage();
        mail.setToAddresses(new String[] {order.Customer_Email__c});
        mail.setSubject('Your Order');
        mail.setPlainTextBody('Thank you for your order!');
        Messaging.sendEmail(new Messaging.SingleEmailMessage[] { mail });
    }
}
```

Fig. 2: A Flow Chart of the Salesforce Business Logic

IV. REENGINEERING BUSINESS LOGIC INTO APEX

The reengineering would be translating .NET business logic into Apex, the Salesforce programming language. The following are the steps to do so:

- i. Convert Methods to Apex:** Convert all methods in the .NET code to an Apex method. Make sure the same logic is preserved, but rewritten to the syntax of Apex and the constraints of the platform within Salesforce.
 - ii. Implementing Validation Rules:** recreation of any validation logic within Salesforce must be done using validation rules or through Apex methods.
 - iii. Data Persistence:** Replace direct calls to the database with Salesforce's data manipulation language (DML) operations, which include insert, update, delete, and upsert.
- The pseudocode for Apex business logic is presented in the table below.

TABLE 3 THE APEX BUSINESS LOGIC

```
// Salesforce Apex Business Logic
public class OrderProcessor {
    public void processOrder(Order__c order) {
        if (isValid(order)) {
            saveOrder(order);
            notifyCustomer(order);
        }
    }
    private Boolean isValid(Order__c order) {
        // Logic to validate order
        return order != null && order.Status__c == 'New';
    }
    private void saveOrder(Order__c order) {
        // Logic to save order in Salesforce
        insert order;
    }
    private void notifyCustomer(Order__c order) {
        // Logic to send notification to the customer
        Messaging.SingleEmailMessage mail = new Messaging.SingleEmailMessage();
        mail.setToAddresses(new String[] {order.Customer_Email__c});
        mail.setSubject('Your Order');
        mail.setPlainTextBody('Thank you for your order!');
        Messaging.sendEmail(new Messaging.SingleEmailMessage[] { mail });
    }
}
}
```

V. IMPLEMENTING SALESFORCE INTEGRATIONS

Very often, Salesforce will need to be integrated with external systems like older databases, third-party services, or other cloud platforms [9][10][11]. The main steps of integrating such systems is illustrated in the section below.

- a. Using the power of Salesforce APIs:** All external communications can be done using the Salesforce REST/SOAP APIs. For example, suppose there is some .NET system integrated with an ERP; the same could be done for Salesforce using its API power.
- b. Creating Apex callouts:** Use the Apex HTTP callouts to make requests against the external services. Be sure to handle the limits on callouts properly by applying asynchronous processing.
- c. Using Middleware:** In complex scenarios of integration, middleware—in particular, MuleSoft or Informatica in this case—can be put in to handle and transform the data between Salesforce and external systems.

Fig. 3 integration architecture diagram

VI. TESTING AND VALIDATION

Testing is required to confirm that the re-engineered business logic in Salesforce works. This is a multi-step process as discussed below.

- i. Unit Testing in Apex:** The test classes written in Apex test the functionality of every method. Since Salesforce requires 75% code coverage for deployment, unit testing will be imperative.
- ii. Data Migration Testing:** Test data integrity in case of any migration of data from .NET onto Salesforce. Validate that all business rules are consistently applied.
- iii. UAT:** Run business users through testing of the reengineered logic in a sandbox, gather feedback, and iterate to put a shine on the implementation.

The code snippet below presents a pseudocode for Apex unit tests.

TABLE 4 APEX UNIT TESTS

```

// Example Apex Unit Test
@isTest
public class OrderProcessorTest {
    @isTest
    static void testProcessOrder() {
        Order__c order = new Order__c();
        order.Status__c = 'New';
        order.Customer_Email__c = 'customer@example.com';
        Test.startTest();
        OrderProcessor processor = new OrderProcessor();
        processor.processOrder(order);
        Test.stopTest();

        // Assertions
        System.assertNotEquals(null, [SELECT Id FROM Order__c WHERE Id = :order.Id]);
    }
}

```

VII. DEPLOYMENT AND MONITORING

In the final step, deploy the reengineered business logic into production and set up monitoring to ensure everything works seamlessly.

- i. One can use change sets for deployment in Salesforce, through either the UI or the Metadata API. Make sure to configure all dependencies under the deployment.
- ii. Put in place Salesforce monitoring tools, like Debug Logs, Health Check, and Event Monitoring, for monitoring to track the usage and performance of the new logic.
- iii. The system should be continuously monitored for improvements post-deployment, and feedback shall be elicited. Implement iterative updates from time to time so that functionality can be enhanced or any lapses corrected.

The monitoring process is summarized in the figure below.

Fig. 4 The post deployment monitoring process

VIII. CONCLUSION

This reengineering, however, was .NET business logic to Salesforce—a complex task with high returns. It needs minute planning and execution. Seamless transitions that will help tap into the full potential of Salesforce's capabilities can be achieved by organizations just through careful mapping of existing business processes and translating .NET logic into Salesforce-compatible code using best practices for integration. The requirement of pseudocodes, flowcharts, and architecture diagrams in all these processes will not just help to explain what the transformation would involve in more detail, but will prescript a more organized and systematic approach. Expected obstacles in terms of the compatibility of data, optimization of performance, and function alignment could be foreseen, but how to deal with such issues can be approached with a thorough and methodical strategy that will lead to successful integration. Ultimately, this reengineering process would not only make the business systems more operationally effective but also open the avenue toward more agile and scalable solutions, thereby driving future growth and innovation within any organization.

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